

**WILL COLLABORATIVE THINK AND DO-ACTIVITY
ENHANCE STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN
CHEMISTRY? A FIELD REPORT**

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Abstract

The study investigated if collaborative think and do-activity will enhance senior secondary students' academic performance in Chemistry. A sample of 152 Senior Secondary 2 Students from 4 senior secondary schools in Ado Local Government Area of Ekiti State, Nigeria was used. The study adopted non-equivalent quasi-experimental research design. The instrument used for data collection was Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) with the reliability value of 0.93 using Kuder-Richardson. Two research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance. The findings of the study revealed that there is significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity and those taught using discussion method in favour of collaborative think and do-activity [$F(1,149)=188.100, p<0.05$]. It is found that there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity [$F(1,76)=163.100, P>0.05$]. It also revealed that the interaction effect between strategies and gender on the mean academic performance scores of students in Chemistry is not statistically significant [$F(1,149)= 427.100, P >0.050$]. It was recommended that collaborative think and do-activity should be adopted while teaching Chemistry since it has been proved to be a viable option in enhancing students' academic performance for regardless of gender.

Keywords: Collaborative think and do-activity, students' academic performance, Chemistry.

Introduction

Education is one of the most crucial instruments for achieving national development and in all countries of the world it is seen as the corner stone of development. In Nigeria, Education has been acknowledged as the key that unlocks national development. This is clearly acknowledged by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2008) which states in her National Policy on Education that education is an instrument “par excellence” for effective national development. Every nation craves for science and technological advancement which can be achieved through the medium of education (Ajewole, 2006). The level of scientific attainment of any nation is an important index for measuring its level of development. Science is the knowledge obtained from the systematic study of the structure and behaviour of the physical world, especially by observing, measuring and experimenting and the development of theories to describe the results of these activities (Ajayi & Ogbeba, 2017). Science education is the field concerned with sharing scientific knowledge, and methods with people not traditionally considered part of the scientific community.

In cognizance with the importance of science and technology, Science subjects such as chemistry are taught in senior secondary schools in Nigeria to provide student with the basic knowledge in chemical concepts and principles through efficient selection of content and sequential and also to provide a reasonable and adequate foundation for a post-secondary school Chemistry course. Despite the importance of Chemistry, it is regrettable that there is a public outcry due to poor performance in sciences subjects such as Chemistry. Poor performance in chemistry in external examinations invariably implies that the nation’s quest for science and technological advancement may not achieve, if solutions that could improve students’ performance are not provided. Studies such as

studies by Usman (2011); Ajayi, Achor and Agogo (2017); Ajayi (2019) revealed that student’s negative attitude towards chemistry and poor teaching methods adopted by teacher are some of the factors that could hinder students’ performance. Therefore, chemistry teachers should adopt innovative strategies such as collaborative think and do-activity strategy that would enable the students to understand whatever concepts, topics or principle that are being taught. Think and do-activity strategy is the exploration of science which develops learner’s abilities to plan, effect, interpret, draw inferences and communicate the outcome of the activities.

Thinks and do activity is an instructional strategy where students think about an event (providing answers to probing questions based on their thinking) and do (carry out) a laboratory experiment or classroom activity and are required to compare their observations with their initial thought, thereby enhancing conceptual understanding of scientific knowledge. Critical thinking skills are applied in interpreting the challenge, recalling relevant experiences and designing a solution. This involves negotiations with others as well as clearly sorting out what procedures will be followed and items of equipment that will be used. It also requires the group to plan what they will be observing and measuring and how this may be done effectively. Otuka (2010) emphasizes that, the aims of the philosophy behind “Think and Do” is to; build on a learner’s inherent inquisitiveness and curiosity; develop and channel a child’s need to find out what will happen; encourage a learner to think about the challenge given by the questions posed by the teacher; undertake the investigation in the classroom to give first-hand exploration; meet the challenge within the parameters set; discuss and plan what to do to reach the target outcome; interpret results, relating one factor to another and

and draw conclusions; identify simple variations; familiarize the learners with science materials; and provide positive practice in manipulative skills.

Collaborative learning is an umbrella for a variety of educational strategies involving joint efforts by both teachers and learners (Ajayi, Achor & Otor, 2019). Collaborative learning engages learners in active learning where they work and learn together in small groups to accomplish shared goals. The ever-growing importance of complex problem solving and knowledge construction in modern society emphasizes the need for collaborative activities and settings in schools to foster learning and collective competencies. In this study, think and do activity have been integrated into collaborative learning activities to facilitate productive collaborative learning. In this regard, think and do-activity in collaborative setting is defined as an instructional strategy where two or more learners in a small group setting are engaged in thinking about an event (students provides answers to probing questions raised by the teacher based on their thinking) and do (carry out) a laboratory experiment or classroom activity and are required to compare their observations with their initial thought, thereby enhancing conceptual understanding of scientific knowledge. The use of think and do-activity in the classroom is a powerful tool to help combat the inertia that has crept into our classrooms. Think and do-activity in the classroom can help to develop divergent thinking skills, inventive creativity, cognitive thinking skills (Annarella, 2013).

Statement of the Problem

Over the years, there have been comments on poor quality of secondary school products in Nigeria. Evidence available from WAEC and NECO results and research findings show that students have been performing poorly in chemistry in external examinations such as

WAEC and NECO. Research effort has shown that the problem is caused by poor teaching method adopted by teachers. Most Nigerian Chemistry teachers use discussion method most frequently in their Chemistry classrooms which results into rote learning and regurgitation of facts, with the indication that such instructional methods have not been adequate at improving students' performance. Therefore, there is a need to make sure that Chemistry is properly taught most especially the difficult concepts using innovative strategy such as collaborative think and do-activity in order to enhance students' performance. Because of these gaps, the study investigated if collaborative think and do-activity could enhance students' academic performance in Chemistry.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate if collaborative think and do-activity could enhance students' academic performance in Chemistry. Specifically, the study;

1. Investigated the effect of collaborative think and do-activity on students' academic performance in Chemistry.
2. Investigated the difference in effect of collaborative think and do-activity between male and female students' academic performance in Chemistry.
3. Investigated the interaction effect between strategies and gender on students' academic performance in Chemistry.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity and those taught using discussion method?
2. What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity?

3. What is the mean interaction effect of treatments and gender on students' performance in Organic Chemistry?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity and those taught using discussion method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity.
3. The interaction effect between strategies and gender on the mean academic performance scores of students in Chemistry is not statistically significant.

Research Design and Procedure

The study used pre-test, post-test non-equivalent quasi experimental design. The pre-test score constituted the covariant of the post-test scores. The study area was Ado Local Government Area of Ekiti State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 8,637 Senior Secondary II students in the 47 government coeducational approved secondary schools. One hundred and fifty-two (152) students were purposively sampled from 4 schools. One instrument known as Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) was used to collect data for this study. CPT is a researcher made instrument that contains two sections. Section A contains bio-data information of the respondents, while section B contains 40 multi choice objective items to which respondents are expected to provide the correct answer by ticking the correct options (A-D).

Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) was validated by three experts of Science Education and two experts in Measurement and Evaluation all from Benue State University, Makurdi. Corrections and suggestions arising from these

experts were used to review the instrument before it was used. Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) was used to obtain the CPT reliability, which yielded a coefficient value of 0.93. The conduct of the study took place during the normal school lesson periods. The time-table of the schools for the study were followed. Before the commencement of the actual treatment, the researcher used one week for the training of the Chemistry teachers who served as research assistants. The training programme was to ensure the homogeneity of instructional situation across all groups. The training for the experimental group only differs from that of the control group by the use of collaborative think and do-activity. The sample was divided into two groups namely; experimental and control group.

During lessons, the experimental group was taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity in line with lessons procedure prepared by the researcher while the control group was taught the same Chemistry topics using the modified lecture lesson notes which lasted for four weeks. The study covers three sub-topics under Chemistry which includes carbon and its compound, electrolysis, redox reactions selected from the SSII scheme of work. The choice of the sub-topics was to help students overcome the difficulties associated with achievement in Chemistry as one of the areas that stand out as problem areas to Chemistry students in the report by the Chief Examiner's for West African Examination Council (2017/2018). Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) was administered as pre-test by the researcher with the assistance of the sampled schools Chemistry teachers which lasted for one week. Then, the actual teaching commences which lasted for four weeks. At the end of these periods, the pre-CPT, were reshuffled and administered as post-tests which lasted for one week and the post tests were marked by the research assistants using the marking scheme developed by the researcher. The pre-test score constituted the covariant of the post-test scores.

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer to the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of

Research question one

What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-

significance using Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA).

RESULTS

activity and those taught using discussion method? The answer to research question one is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Academic Performance and Standard Deviation Scores of Students using Collaborative think and Do-Activity and Discussion method

Group	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
Collaborative think & Do-Activity	79	10.44	1.19	23.64	1.62	13.20
Discussion method	73	10.42	1.17	14.02	1.39	3.60
Mean difference		0.02		9.62		9.60

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The results in Table 1 reveal that, the pre-test mean scores for collaborative think and do-activity and modified lecture groups are 10.44 and 10.42 with their standard deviation scores of 1.19 and 1.17 respectively. The post-test mean scores accordingly were 23.64 and 14.02 with their

standard deviation scores of 1.62 and 1.39 respectively. The overall mean difference between the two groups was 9.60 in favour of collaborative think and do-activity group. This implies that the students in collaborative think and do-activity had

higher performance than the modified lecture group.

Research question two

What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female

students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity?

The answer to research question two is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean Academic Performance and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students using Collaborative Think and Do-Activity

Gender	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
Male	44	11.05	1.27	24.54	1.42	13.49
Female	35	11.02	1.23	24.21	1.39	13.19
Mean difference		0.03		0.33		0.30

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The results in Table 2 reveal that the male and female students had a mean gain of 13.49 and 13.19 respectively. The mean difference is 0.30. This difference, though small is in favour of the

Research question three

What is the mean interaction effect of treatments and gender on students' performance in

male students. This implies that male students gained slightly higher performance than their female counterparts in the collaborative think and do-activity.

Chemistry? The answer to research question three is presented in figure 1.

Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: TprCPT = 10.4145

Fig 1: Interaction plot of treatments and gender on students' performance in Chemistry

Figure 1 presents a graph of the interaction of treatments and gender on the mean performance scores of students in Chemistry. The graph lines for gender did not intercept which suggests that there was no interactive effect of treatments and gender on students' performance in Chemistry.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity and those taught using discussion method. The test of hypothesis one is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: ANCOVA Result for Mean Performance Scores of Students taught using Collaborative Think and Do-Activity and Discussion method

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	4231.109 ^a	2	229.100	171.110	.000
Intercept	1442.000	1	1442.000	158.001	.000
TPrCPT	153.001	1	153.001	121.001	.000
Group	2521.009	1	2521.009	188.100	.000
Error	649.007	149	7.701		
Total	299015.101	152			
Corrected Total	3972.000	151			

a. R squared = .201 (Adjusted R Squared= .161)

Source: Field Survey, 2019

ANCOVA Test result in Table 3 reveals that there is a significant difference between collaborative think and do-activity and discussion method of teaching in favour of collaborative think and do-activity strategy [F(1,149) =188.100, p<0.05]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that collaborative think and do-activity strategy is

more effective than discussion method in enhancing students' performance in chemistry.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity.

The test of hypothesis two is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: ANCOVA Result for Mean Performance Scores of Male and Female Students taught using Collaborative Think and Do-Activity

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	3582.001 ^a	2	319.001	181.100	.000
Intercept	1872.000	1	1872.000	159.001	.000
TPrCPT	161.001	1	161.001	153.001	.000
Gender	1621.001	1	1621.001	163.100	.221
Error	325.005	76	14.001		
Total	324421.001	79			
Corrected Total	2978.001	78			

a. R squared = .251 (Adjusted R Squared= .199)

Source: Field Survey, 2019

ANCOVA Test results in Table 4 reveal that there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of male and female students taught chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity [$F(1,76) = 163.100$, $P > 0.050$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that collaborative think and

do-activity enhanced both male and female students' academic performance in Chemistry.

Hypothesis Three

The interaction effect between strategies and gender on the mean academic performance scores of students in Chemistry is not statistically significant. The test to hypothesis three is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: ANCOVA Tests for Interaction Effect between Methods and Gender on Students' Performance in Chemistry

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	4371.002 ^a	2	348.001	294.101	.000
Intercept	1782.001	1	1782.001	438.001	.000
TPrCPT	349.100	1	349.100	159.001	.000
Group*Gender	2571.009	1	2511.009	427.100	.192
Error	579.100	149	19.019		
Total	219908.009	152			
Corrected Total	1401.711	151			

a. R squared = .256 (Adjusted R Squared= .231)

Source: Field Survey, 2019

ANCOVA results in Table 5 reveal that the interaction effect between methods and gender on the mean performance scores of students in chemistry is not significant [$F(1,149) = 427.100$, $P > 0.050$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that there is no need for separation of instructional method for male and female students since collaborative think and do-activity can successfully be used to enhance the academic performance of the two groups.

Discussion of findings

The study investigated if collaborative think and do-activity could enhance students' academic performance in Chemistry. The findings of this study revealed that students taught Chemistry using collaborative think and do-activity had higher academic performance than their counterparts taught using discussion method. This finding agrees with Audu, Ajayi, and Angura (2017); Ajayi and Ogbeba (2017) who found that students had higher achievement when exposed to activity-related instructions than their counterparts that were exposed to lecture and discussion methods. This result is in agreement with the study by Nwagbo (2013). The author reported that the use of collaborative think and do-activity in teaching and learning science subjects is superior to use of conventional teaching method. The likely explanation for this outcome may be connected to the fact that the nature of collaborative think and do-activity such as build on a learner's inherent inquisitiveness and curiosity; encourage a learner to collaborative think about the challenge given by the questions posed by the teacher; undertake the investigation in the classroom to give first-hand exploration; meet the challenge within the parameters set; discuss and plan what to do to reach the target outcome; interpret results, relating one factor to another and draw conclusions made it possible to enhance the academic performance of learners

taught with it when compared to the discussion method.

The findings of this study also revealed that there is no statistical significant difference between male and female students' academic performance using collaborative think and do-activity strategy. In the same vein, the finding of this study also revealed that there is no significant interaction effect between methods and gender on mean academic performance scores of students in Chemistry. This implies that, collaborative think and do-activity is superior to the discussion method irrespective of gender in fostering students' academic performance. In this case, there is no need for separation of instructional method for male and female students since collaborative think and do-activity can be used successfully for the two groups.

Conclusion

It is evident from the findings of this study that the use of collaborative think and do-activity is more effective in facilitating and enhancing students' academic performance in Chemistry than discussion method. By implication, this affirmed that students' academic performance in chemistry depend on the method of instruction. It is also evident from the findings of this study that no gender disparity exists in the performance of male and female chemistry students using collaborative think and do-activity. Thus, collaborative think and do-activity is significantly a very useful instructional strategy for meaningful learning and enhances academic performance of students regardless of their gender.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Collaborative think and do-activity should be adopted by Chemistry teachers for teaching, since it has been proved to be a viable option in enhancing students' academic performance in Chemistry.

2. Conferences, seminars, and workshops should be organised through Ministry of Education, schools administrators and professional bodies such as Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) to sensitize Chemistry teachers with a view to improving their skills and experiences on the usage of collaborative think and do-activity strategy aimed at developing students' academic performance in Chemistry.
3. Collaborative think and do-activity is not gender sensitive; therefore, both male and female students should be exposed to collaborative think and do-activity to enhance their academic performance in Chemistry.

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